

International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)

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Do Tensions in the South China Sea Herald the Collapse of Global Supply Chains? [Full Text](#)

Gilles Paché, Aix-Marseille University, France

Integrating Robotics for Enhanced Business Operations [Full Text](#)

Ravindra Kumar Patro, Zum Services Inc., USA

Emerging Technologies for Precision Supply Chain Management [Full Text](#)

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The screenshot displays the website interface for the International Journal of Managing Value And Supply Chains (IJMVSC). The header includes the journal title, ISSN information (0976 - 979X [Online]; 2230 - 7966 [Print]), and a navigation menu with links for Home, Editorial, Current Issue, Submission, Indexing, Special Issue, Contacts, and AIRCC. The main content area is titled 'Current Issue' and highlights 'September 2024, Volume 15, Number 3'. A list of articles is shown, each with a 'Full Text' button. The articles listed are: 'Do Tensions in the South China Sea Herald the Collapse of Global Supply Chains?' by Gilles Paché, 'Integrating Robotics for Enhanced Business Operations' by Ravindra Kumar Patro, and 'Emerging Technologies for Precision Supply Chain Management' by Ravindra Kumar Patro. On the right side, there is a 'Forthcoming Papers' section listing '2024, Volume 15, Number 3', '2024, Volume 15, Number 2', and '2024, Volume 15, Number 1', along with an 'Archives' link.